

NUMERICAL STUDY FOR TWO-PHASE LAMINAR FLOW IN A SUDDENLY EXPANDING CHANNEL

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Abstract. *The article explores a method for adapting the computational grid to solving two-dimensional Navier-Stokes differential equations, which describe the physical processes of gas dynamics specifically for the problem of a two-dimensional channel with an expansion coefficient $(H/h) = 2$. Different flow characteristics were calculated at different Reynolds numbers $Re =$ from 100 to 1000, to get the actual thread behavior. Calculations are performed for laminar flow mode. The results of the longitudinal velocity profiles in different sections of the channel and the length of the primary and secondary vortices are obtained with a change in the Reynolds number after the ledge. For the numerical solution of this problem, a second-order accuracy McCormack scheme was used. To confirm the correctness of the numerical results, a comparison was made with experimental data that were taken from literature sources. It is also shown that as a result of using this method of adaptive grids, it is possible to improve the numerical accuracy obtained for a given number of node points. It is shown that the existing method of multiple 2D adaptive meshes makes it easier to concentrate meshes in the required areas. This method should prove useful for many Navier-Stokes flow calculations.*

Keywords: *Navier–Stokes equations, two-phase flow, separated flow, control volume method.*

Introduction

The study of separated flows is a classic problem in fundamental fluid mechanics. This flow geometry is an important prototype for the study of flow splitting, flow reattachment, and recirculation bubbles. The phenomenon of flow separation is common in engineering applications such as the flow of water past a hydrofoil, the flow of air past compressor and turbine blades, suddenly expanding pipes, and combustion chambers. The geometry of rapidly expanding channels is also an important issue for understanding the instability of divided flow. Fluid flows in sharply expanding channels occur in various technical devices and structures. A sharp change in the geometry of the channel wall or the appearance of the streamlined body can probably lead to a rupture of the flow and also significantly change its kinematic structure. A flow in a flat channel with a sharp expansion belongs to a simple class of separated flows when the separation point of the flow is fixed. Theoretical study and calculation of similar flows presents significant difficulties due to the appearance of complex separated flows and reverse vortices in the area behind the ledge.

In 1910, Blasius [1] analytically studied the laminar separation of stationary two-dimensional flows of an incompressible fluid in straight channels. Further, this problem was considered by many scientists to study the mechanisms of separation flows during observation and experiment of differential schemes for solving the Navier-Stokes equations. Due to their considerable practical significance, existing flows have been theoretically and experimentally studied also for laminar [2-4] and turbulent [5-7] modes of motion of incompressible and compressible fluid. Most studies in this direction focus on flows in channels with bilateral

symmetrical sharp expansion. [8-10]. The experimental data studied for this purpose in a flat channel were obtained in [8, 9], in which the formation of a circulation zone behind the bar was observed. A number of experimental scientists used equations of motion to calculate currents with a sharp expansion when approaching the edge layer [1, 5].

Physical and mathematical formulation of the problem.

We consider laminar flow in a flat two-dimensional channel with sudden expansion. To understand the position of the fluid through the rear-facing stepped channel, the step length is assumed $h=5$ mm. The physical and mathematical meaning of the analyzed laminar flow and the configuration of the computational domain are presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Diagram of the design area in a flat channel with a reverse ledge

Methods

System of nonstationary Navier-Stokes equations and continuity equations with constant density in Cartesian coordinates has the following form [5]:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial U}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial U}{\partial x} + V \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial p}{\rho \partial x} = \frac{1}{\text{Re}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x^2} \right), \\ \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial V}{\partial x} + V \frac{\partial V}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial p}{\rho \partial y} = \frac{1}{\text{Re}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x^2} \right), \\ \frac{\partial U}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial V}{\partial y} = 0. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Here U, V – respectively, the dimensionless longitudinal and vertical components of the laminar flow velocity vector, p – dimensionless hydrostatic pressure, $\text{Re} = HU_0/\nu$ - Reynolds number.

Results

Figure 3 shows the experimental and numerical results of Armali et al. for the longitudinal velocity profile, as well as for the two-fluid model for the Reynolds number $\text{Re}=400$. The numerical results are for the McCormack scheme for both the simple grid and the adaptive grid. Up to $\text{Re}<500$, the experimental and numerical results did not give any additional separation regions other than the main one attached to the stage. Under these conditions, good agreement is achieved between the experiments and the numerical results.

Fig. 3. Profiles of the axial () velocity component: (○) Armali et al. (experiment), (- - -) McCormack scheme

Fig. 4 shows the longitudinal velocity contour for different Reynolds numbers.

T=10

T=20

T=30

Isoline of dimensionless time-averaged velocity

Fig. 4. Change of adaptive grid, velocity field vector and velocity isoline at different times and Reynolds numbers $Re=1000$

Conclusion

This work is a study of methods for adapting the computational grid to solving two-dimensional differential Navier-Stokes equations that describe physical processes of gas dynamics specifically for the problem of a two-dimensional channel with an expansion coefficient $(H/h) = 2$. The equidistribution method was used to construct a dynamic adaptive grid. Particular attention was paid to increasing the accuracy of the solution obtained on the adaptive grid. Based on the theoretical study, algorithms for solving the Navier-Stokes equations on an adaptive grid in two-dimensional formulations were developed.

The operation of the modules was tested on 2D gas dynamics problems that had experimental solutions. For all considered cases, the solutions obtained on the adaptive grid resolved the gas-dynamic features of the problems well and were stable. The calculation results showed that the use of an adaptive grid in comparison with a fixed one leads to a significant decrease in the mean square error of the solution and a reduction in the time spent on the calculation, which indicates the operability and effectiveness of the proposed algorithms. The paper shows the influence of the McCormack finite-difference scheme with the SIMPLE procedure for studying separation processes. As a result of a detailed numerical study of flow velocity fields, the patterns of formation of the vortex structure of the flow in a flat channel with steps are shown, including secondary vortex formations and non-stationary separated flow regimes.

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